

The Centralised University Money: A seamless cashless transaction system for a campus

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Abstract:

The Centralized University Money can be used on campus to make purchases using an ID card. The cards will make it possible to make payments without using a bank card and to conduct cashless transactions. All university students have access to the card, which can be loaded with money in advance. Either a central server on campus or blockchain technology can be used for financial administration. Due to the lack of high-speed internet on college campuses, this will do away with the requirement for cash transactions and smartphone transactions. Each cafeteria or store will have a Point-of-Sale (PoS) system that is linked to the university's central server or to the blockchain. Every time a student swipes their ID on a POS, they will be prompted to enter a pin before they can make a quick payment without using cash or a mobile device. The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) University ID will contain the register number of the students. The reason we are considering the use of blockchain technology is that it can allow the ledgering of transactions in a more secure way than a centralized server. This setup will reduce the number of failed transactions inside the campus and enable the flow of money in a much easier manner.

Keywords: